

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B207
Date: 7th June 2006
Take Off: 14:47:56
Landing: 16:30:06
Flight Time: 1h42m10

Campaign: CAPEX (AEROPOR & VPRACOP)

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: Beja area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
7	Filters	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	Core Chemistry/CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
10	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office
11	CCN	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
12	Wet Neph	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
14	Mission 2	Frank Wagner	University of Evora
15	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
16	VPRACOP 1/Filters	Mario Reis	Instituto Tecnologico e Nuclear, Sacavem
17	VPRACOP 1/Filters	Joao Oliveira	Instituto Tecnologico e Nuclear, Sacavem
18	CLAPREC	Piotr Drzweicki	University of Warsaw
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B207 Track 07-JUN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B207
 Date: 07th June 2006
 Project: CAPEX
 Location: Beja region, Portugal

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
142627		event	0.56 kft	107	INU to Nav
144252		event	0.57 kft	033	start taxi
144338		ASP	0.57 kft	324	open on taxi
144756		T/O	0.96 kft	186	
144855	150317	Profile 1	1.5 - 20.0 kft	185	
145043		event	5.2 kft	178	Nev. zero
145146		event	6.7 kft	176	JW zero
145306		Video	8.3 kft	177	start FFC, DFC
150318	150626	Profile 2	20.0 - 18.0 kft	033	
150831	151444	Profile 2	18.1 - 11.0 kft	212	
151520	152220	Run 1.1	11.0 kft	257	
151919		event	11.0 kft	257	Nev zero
152210		event	11.0 kft	259	JW zero
152629	152938	Profile 3	11.0 - 7.8 kft	157	
153029	153730	Run 2.1	7.8 kft	079	
154140	154237	Orbit 1	7.8 kft	001	
154447	154549	Orbit 1.2	7.8 - 7.7 kft	273	
154712	155140	Profile 4	7.7 - 5.0 kft	266	
155219	155315	Orbit 2.1	5.1 - 5.0 kft	306	
155613	160313	Run 3.1	5.0 kft	087	
160313	160648	Profile 5	5.0 - 2.5 kft	086	
160835	160953	Profile 6	2.6 - 1.5 kft	258	
160948	162125	Run 4.1	1.5 kft	267	
163006		Land	0.59 kft	005	163006
163559		Shutdown posn	0.58 kft	114	38 05.13N 07 55.56W

B207 Track 07-JUN-06

SORTIE BRIEF

Flight No: B207
Date: 07/06/2006

Briefing: 14:00L
T/O: 16:00L, Land: 17:30L

Programme: EUFAR (European Fleet for Airborne Research)
Project: CAPEX (Clouds and Aerosols over Portugal Experiment) May/June 2006

SORTIE: Desert Dust Aerosols & Clear Skies (Mainly AEROPOR, VPRACOP)

Conditions/Weather:

Ideally clear skies, 2/8 Cu is acceptable

Trial Objectives:

Measure particles arriving from the African Desert in several layers

Background information:

Lidar at Évora (10 UTC) determined 3 aerosol layers: SFC-1km = Boundary layer, 1.5-2.0km, 2.5-4.5km, aerosol optical thickness at Évora (07 UTC): 0.170 @440nm, 0.112 @870nm, Angstrom=0.61; aot at Beja (08:30 -11:00 UTC) 0.25 @440nm, 0.16 @870nm, Angstrom=0.65.

Location:

Around local Beja area.

Flight Pattern

- 1) Depart Beja and perform profile ascent from lowest height up to FL200 (above the higher aerosol layer) at 1000FT/min. Determine aerosol vertical profile.
- 2) Make S&L runs, 7min each, down sun or into sun if possible above, in and below each aerosol/dust layer. Additionally make orbit (clockwise) below each aerosol/dust layer, aligned with solar zenith angle. It is expected to have 1 or 2 aerosol/dust layers. If only 1 aerosol/dust layer present, perform 2 runs in aerosol/dust layer, and perform orbits in and below aerosol/dust layer.
- 3) Return to Beja.

Mission Scientist Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. B207 AEROPOR (Aerosol/Dust) & VPRACOP filter sampling .
Date: 07/06/2006 In Beja local area.

Assessment of the Flight:

Overall, a short but successful sortie (1 hr 42 min) examining the pollution/haze/dust/aerosol layers near and in vicinity of Beja.

We had problems with the Vis channel part of the SWS during the first part of the flight (during the main profile ascent & into Run 1.1), but this was overcome during this run (1.1) and SWS & SHIMS remained functional through the rest of the flight. The NOx analyser failed during the middle part of the flight - Kate to investigate post flight. No other instrument faults were reported. [The sampling time for CCN samples was taking more than 10 mins at upper levels].

Weather conditions were good. Skies were totally clear except for a trace of Cu (small vertical extent) convection, and a trace of Ac to east near the start of the sortie. Winds were mostly moderate, SSW/ly – SSE/ly. There was a general Aerosol/Dust layer extending from the surface up to FL100 (seen visually, and confirmed by Tephigram inversion/hydrolapse and by changes in CVI and PCASP (Cloud Physics) count changes. Within this layer, there were some lateral and vertical (banding) changes in aerosol/dust thickness.

After T/O at 1448z from Beja, we went very swiftly into P1, a full profile ascent from 1500 ft to FL150 at 1000 ft/m, heading out to E, then returning towards Beja. After profiling down to FL 110, (P2), at 1000 ft/min, we then worked the following levels:

1. FL110, about 1000 ft above top of aerosol layer, Run 1.1 into sun, about 7 minutes, extended to try and get CCN to complete its sampling.
2. After profiling down to 7750 ft (P3), we performed run 2.1 (downsun), followed by 2 Orbits, O1.1 & O 1.2, clockwise, 60 deg angle of bank.
3. After profiling down to 5000 ft (P4), we performed Orbit O 2.1, clockwise, 60 deg angle of bank, followed by Run 3.1, downsun.
4. After profiling down to 2500 ft, (P5), then down to 1500 ft (P6), we made a final run (R 4.1) into sun .
5. A climb to 5000 ft to rapidly prepare all for landing, was followed by a landing at exactly 1630z . A very distinct smoke plume was seen SSW of the Beja military site on approach to landing.

DRK.
07/06/06

Mission Scientist's Log

ASLO Per (Aerosol / Dust layers).

Flight No **B207**.....

Date **07/06/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1443		START	TAR 1.		Wind 150° / 17 kts (from Tower)
1448		T/O	BETA		TR of CW to North.
144855	^{START} P1	1500'	150°		Start P1 at 1500' (1000'/min)
1450	Passing 3000'				Hiz-, generally
145450	P1 ↑	FL 100	147°	37°30' N 7°48' W	Passing FL 100 PCASP particles not? Wind 210° / 23 m/sec Inversion / hydro layer / Aerosol CVI change } Top at FL 100
PROBLEMS WITH SWS (S4 INS OK)					vis channel (IR OK) - Will continue with mission
150318	END P1	FL 200	035°	38°0' N 7°18' W	End P1 & reverse dir to P2
150626	Inter P2	FL 180			Interrupt P2 at FL 180 return ↓
150631	Resume P2	FL 180	220°	36°6' N 7°6' W	Resume P2
151444	End P2	FL 110	215°	37°54' N 7°24' W	End P2
151520	START R1.1	FL 110	259°	37°44' N 7°30' W	Start R1.1. [SWS IR channel still NOT WORKING]
← SWS Now BACK WORKING OK					tox analyser failed. CCW still cycling, will extend run.
152220	END R1.1	FL 110	-	37°48' N 8°0' W	End R1.1 } Turn & track above this altitude to try get CCW sample complete Haze / Aerosol layer just below ✓ TOXIC Co below (weak vertical extent) TOXIC Ac to East, otherwise OKC. CCW still not working ∴ descend to 750'!
152629	START P3	FL 110	157°	38°0' N 7°48' W	Start P3 ↓ 1000'/min
		9500' - 9700'			Main top of Aerosol / Dust layer (CVI PCASP VISUAL)
152938	END P3	7.7 kft		37°54' N 7°42' W	End P3 Wind 179° / 16 m/sec
153029	START 2.1	7.7 kft	062°	37°54' N 7°30' W	Start Run 2.1 at 7750'. DOWNSUN
153605					Some structure in Aerosol / dust from CVI (peak about 30 secs ago).

601
A2.0 →
261.
downsun
7

Mission Scientist's Log

CVI

Flight No **B.207**.....

Date **07/06/06**.....

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
153730	END 2-1	7750'	/	38° 3' N 7° 6' W	End Run 2-1 at 7750'.
153850			→		CVI has 7/5 sample, will continue to maneuver for ~2 min Air is dry, so will not complete sample.
154140	START ORB 1-1	7750'	019°	38° 0' N 7° 15' W	
154237	END 01-1	7750'			End Orbit 1-1 60°.
154447	START ORB 1-2	7750'		38° 0' N 7° 24' W	SWS needs 2 nd orbit to get correct values Start Orbit 1-2 60° for SWS
154537	hit own wake				End Orbit 1-2.
154549					Prepare to descend to 5000'.
154712	P4	7750'	266°		Start Profile P4 ↓ 1000' / min to 5000'
1551	PA	5000'	266°	38° 0' N 7° 45' W	End P4 at 5000'.
155229	START ORB 2-1	5000'			Start Orbit 2-1 at 5000'.
155315	END 0-2	5000'		38° 6' N 7° 34' W	End Orb 2-1.
155813	START ORB 2-3	5000'	065°	38° 6' N 7° 54' W	Start Run 3-1 at 5000'. David Sun (7 min)
160323	START ORB 2-3	5000' ↓	067°	38° 6' N 7° 15' W	End R3-1, start P5 ↓ to 2500'. Will descend to 2500' & do final run with data (hopefully below haze/ice/aurora layer)
		4000'		→	Aerosol ↑
		3710'		→	Aerosol still ↑.
		2800'		→	New feature.
		2500'			
160645	END P5				End P5 at 2500' still high values of aerosol (P5ASD)
					∴ Will descend now to 1500'.
160835	START P6	2500'	263°	38° 6' N 7° 6' W	Start P6, 2500' ↓ 1500'.

downward 2650' A2.

A2 2650'

160948 GWS P6 START 4-1 1500' 268°

End P6 START Run 4-1 at 1500'. Intrusion. (Aerosol values much same at this height as at 2500')

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B207

Date : 07/06/06

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	None
O₃	None
NO_x	No flow through Ozonator at FL100 and above. Instrument switched off to prevent possible damage.
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT # T _E	TEMP INLET T _b	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF	7800'	T _b	1	2	3	4	5	
15:15:20	15:16:00			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	RUN 2-1
		27.57	25.32	0.16	0.30				S Run ended
15:30:29	15:31:15	27.52	24.74	277	332	INSUFFICIENT TIME ALLOWED TO COMPLETE			D before analysis completed
				224	237				B
				2420	2408				R
				991.0	991				P
		5000'							RUN 3-1
15:56:13	15:57:10	26.32	23.80	0.17	0.31	0.48	0.8	1.08	S Analysis
		25.61	22.67	308	508	828	1227	1546	D completed
		25.47	21.70	260	253	310	307	480	B in descent
		25.34	19.87	2371	2387	2381	2352	2344	R from sample
				993.1	993.1	993.0	993.1	993.2	P 3 to end
		1500'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
16:09:48	16:10:30	25.22	22.84	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.70	1.08	S RUN
		24.92	22.0	272	777	1029	1901	3639	D 4-1
		24.90	21.2	223	227	222	240	413	B
		24.89	20.43	2318	2323	2323	2319	2330	R
		24.80	19.37	993.3	993.3	993.3	993.3	993.3	P Bouncy
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

unable to compare
michelson

ARIES flight log

Flight: B207

Location: CAPEX, BEDA Portugal

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Date: 06/7/06

Operator(s): Joss Kern

Resolution: 2

Gain A: 2

B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Sshr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
151439	R1-1	B207D	Clsd	70.7	30.9	18.2	-189.9	36.0	CH1 x 2	151526
151600	R1-1	B207E	open						Z1 x 2	
151723	R1-1	B207F	Clsd						N1 x 4	
151930	R1-1	B207G	Clsd						N1 x 4 N1 x 4	1522
152134	R1-1	B207H	Clsd	70.8	30.7	15.3	-190.6	31.4	CH1	
152825	R2	B207I	Clsd	71.2	30.9	15.6	-190.6	32.3	CH1	Renamed data files to B207, from B207, ops!
153104	R2-1	B207J	open						Z1 x 4	
153306	R2-1	B207K	open						Z1 x 4	
153512	R2-1	B207L	Clsd						N1 x 2	
153633	R2-1	B207M	Clsd	71.5	30.9	18.6	-190.6	29.3	CH1 x 2	
153842	R3-1 start	B207N	Clsd	71.0	30.9	21.3	-189.9	31.8	CH1 x 2	
154613	R3-1	B207O	open						Z1 x 4	
154818	R3-1	B207P	open						Z1 x 4	
160025	R3-1	B207Q	Clsd						N1 x 2	
160140	R3-1	B207R	Clsd	70.8	32.0	23.4	-190.6	30.4	CH1	
160822	R6	B207S	Clsd	71.0	31.2	24.3	-190.6	31.9	CH1	
160950	R4-1	B207T	open						Z1 x 4	
161159	R4-1	B207U	open						Z1 x 4	
161408	R4-1	B207V	Clsd						N1 x 2	

161527 R4-1 B207W Clsd 71.0 33.8 24.3 -190.6 32.4 CH1 x 2
 161654 R4-1 B207X Clsd N1 x 2 muller/Jan

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	7/6/06	Flight	B207	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAPEX		
Departure	Beja	Arrival	Beja		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	09:53:04
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	23°C	Ch	23°C	Ch18	22°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	09:56:55
Initial target temperatures	Hot	297.6	Cold	304.1		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	09:59:07
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not Fitted					
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	
Weather	Cloud	Low pollution	Precip	None		
	Surface	Dry	Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	13:40:00		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot				Cold
	Deimos:	Hot				Cold
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						•
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						•
System running again					at time	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.207**.....

 Date **07/06/06**.....

 Operator's name: **Wilson**.....

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GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
145300	P1							data start. Ascending to FL200
145822	Ascent	FL150	11.9	2.1	16	—	10°	
150318	P2	FL200	14.2	0	12.6	—	10°	
150626	P2	FL180	14.8	0	12.2	—	10°	int P2 @ 180
150831	P2	FL180	15.1	0	12			restart P2 → FL110
151444	P2			1.1	15.7	↘	10°c	end P2.
151520	R1.1	FL110	12.9	1.1	15.7	→	10°c	start R1.1. Set temp ramp up to 43°c.
151740	R1.1	110	12.8	1.5	32	↗	38°c	
152220	R1.1	FL110	12.9	5.0	88	→	43°c	end R1.1
152340			13.1	4.7	83	↘	43°c	start ramping water temp down for next run.
152626	P3	FL110	13.2	4.1	37	↘	27°c	start P3 → FL077
152938	P3	FL0775	13.3	17	30	↘	20°c	end P3
153039	R2.1	FL0775	13.3	15.1	30.8	↗	20°c	start R2.1 @ 7750ft. Water ramping up. to 44°c
153355	R2.1	---	13.4	20	68	→	43°c	
153730	R2.1	---	11.4	15.1	75	→	44°c	end R2.1
154140	orbit 1	---						start orbit 1 @ 60° AOB 240kts
154237	---	---	12.0	21	78	→	43	end orbit 1
154447	orbit 1.2	---	12.1	19	79	→	44	start orbit 1.2 60° AOB
154549	---	---						end orbit 1.2. set water to +15. Humidity sampling down.
154712	P4	---	12.2	24	62	↘	33	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 207 Date: 7th June 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	Y
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N	Racks:	
FWVS	N	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	Y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI	Y
“ Red	Y	(CVI includes PCASP)	
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera	N		
TAFTS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
MARSS	Y	AVAPS	N
DEIMOS	N	IR Camera	N
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B207

Date: 7th June 2006

Instruments

1. SATCOM-C reports "system clock error in CMOS clock." Turn-around message received in pre-flight check.
2. SWS: failure early in flight but problem rectified
3. ARIES: stepper motor 180 deg out of alignment: returned to service prior to flight.
4. Core Chemistry: Nox, ozonator failed during flight.

Aircraft

Large amount of insect debris on FFC

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B207:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting completion of post flight processing
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

1 x Forward Facing Cameras
1 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dave Kindred

EU Aircraft Liaison Officer
Observations Based Research
Jupiter Wing J-M-W014
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E-mail: dave.kindred@metoffice.gov.uk

BEJA,

AFWA MM5 Output 1 1.5

	Pressure	Height	W Dir	W Speed
3	990	687	195	6
	975	1131	190	12
	950	1861	185	13
	925	2644	180	13
4	900	3423	175	13
	875	4217	165	13
	850	5029	160	14
	800	6714	170	21
	750	8491	185	29
	700	10366	185	36
6	650	12352	190	38
	600	14463	195	39
	550	16717	200	41
	500	19144	205	42
8	450	21775	215	44
	400	24645	220	46
	350	27807	220	49
	300	31344	215	49
10	250	35375	215	46
	200	40091	220	42
	150	45968	235	38
	100	54206	250	22

Lid Strength Index = 4.96732
 Thickness 1000mb - 500mb = 5716m
 Thickness 1000mb - 850mb = 1413m
 SWEAT = 171
 Environ. Helicity = 29
 Storm Rel. Helicity = 199

 CAPE = 764
 K Index = 22
 Total Totals = 46
 Lifted Index = -2
 Convective Inhibition = 77
 Max UWV = 0.0260146 at 500mb
 Mean Rel Humid 1000-500mb = 48%
 Lapse Rate 850mb - 500mb = 8.31C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 500mb = 8.85C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 400mb = 8.96C/Km
 Precipitable Water = 1.13in
LCL
 018 HR FCST SKEW-T
 18Z 07-JUN-2006

GRID PNT LAT = 38.15 LON = -7.68
 STATION LAT = 38.016 LON = -7.866

AFWA LPFR-NE MM5 15Km

RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C) FL Visibility (statue miles)

VALID:12Z07JUN2006

ICING LGT MDT SVR

LPFR

Note: Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight.

NE

AFWA LPFR-NE MM5 15Km

RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C) FL Visibility (statue miles)

VALID:18Z07JUN2006

ICING

LGT

MDT

SVR

LPFR

Note: Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight.

NE

AFWA LPST-SE MM5 15Km

RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C) FL Visibility (statue miles)

VALID:18Z07JUN2006

ICING LGT MDT SVR

LPST **Note:** Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight. **SE**